

Synthesizing nano anti-inflammatory, antioxidant medication using Turmeric Reduced Copper Nano

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With increasing rates of obesity, diabetes and aging population worldwide, chronic wounds are becoming increasingly common. Prolonged chronic wounds need periodic dressing changes; however wound dressings seem to be passive players in wound management. The healing process can be hastened if the bandages used to dress or cover wounds are coated with anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidant. Copper has significant anti-microbial, anti-bacterial capabilities and can destroy a variety of microorganisms. It has also been proven to promote the development of new blood vessels, which aids wound healing. Copper nanoparticles can be synthesized in various methods such as chemical reduction, thermal decomposition, laser ablation and electron beam radiation. In the past few years, Green Chemistry has been developed for synthesising metal nanoparticles has become a prominent scientific interest. Plant-mediated with copper nanoparticles is preferable to chemical and physical synthesis since it is a non-toxic, cost-effective and ecologically acceptable method. Biological elements such as bacteria yeast fungi, algae and plants are used instead of abrasive, hazardous and costly chemicals. Plants rich in bioactive compounds, such as *Curcuma longa* can be employed as a reducing, stabilizing and capping agents during the Green production of copper nanoparticles. As a result, turmeric appears to be a superior choice for research. Our aim is to investigate the effects of copper impregnation dressings on wound infection. Copper nano will be prepared by using turmeric and other natural ingredients and with the synthesized nano copper bandages will be coated and used as wound dressing to see the acceleration in healing process.

Keywords: Plant-based synthesis, CopperNano, Turmeric